

Project-Based Learning as an Assessment Tool for Statistical Literacy in Non-Mathematics Undergraduates

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Abstract

This study investigates the value of project-based learning as the main assessment strategy in an introductory statistics course taken by undergraduates whose majors lie outside mathematics. Student feedback gathered across multiple consecutive semesters is analysed to understand perceptions of course design, teaching quality, and the authentic project that asks learners to begin with a prescribed statistical method and work backwards to suitable data and research questions. Results show strong approval of assessment transparency and fairness, instructor expertise, constructive feedback, and the relevance of learning resources. Comments indicate that the reversed design of the project deepens understanding of statistical reasoning and underscores the practical relevance of quantitative inquiry. The analysis also uncovers moderate concern about the dominant theory-and-practice-based approach and the organisational demands of group work. The study concludes that a well-planned, real-life project can effectively improve students' understanding of statistics, especially when students have the chance to practice with simple tasks early on and are supported in working together as a team.

Introduction

Statistical literacy encompasses the ability to comprehend, interpret, and critically assess statistical data and information, as well as to effectively communicate and apply statistical reasoning across diverse contexts (Wallmann (1993)). According to Cal's model (2002), statistical literacy consists of two primary components: knowledge elements and dispositional elements. The knowledge elements encompass literacy skills, statistical and mathematical knowledge, contextual understanding, and critical questioning abilities, whereas the dispositional elements include a critical stance alongside beliefs and attitudes. This conceptual framework informs the design and learning objectives of the undergraduate course "Statistics", which is examined in this study (hereafter referred to as "the course"). The course is structured to provide students with a comprehensive understanding of statistical methods and tools, equipping them with the necessary skills to collect, analyze, and interpret data. The intended learning outcomes of the course include using descriptive and inferential statistics terms and methods correctly; formulating research questions in a justified manner and selecting appropriate data analysis methods accordingly; analyzing statistical data using software, applying descriptive and inferential statistical methods; interpreting and critically evaluating datasets and the results of statistical data analysis; and synthesizing and articulating conclusions based on data analysis results.

The course employs a range of assessment methods, among which Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is serving as one of the primary strategies. PjBL engages students in an extended inquiry process, requiring them to investigate and respond to complex questions, challenges, or problems, culminating in the production of a final artefact (in

this case, the project report). Thomas (2000) highlights that PjBL combines academic content with practical applications, promoting both knowledge acquisition and the development of essential soft skills, including collaboration and presentation. Investigating real-world statistical problems reflects the inquiry-driven essence of PjBL, reinforcing its alignment with authentic learning experiences. The defence of the final report further reinforces accountability, critical thinking, and effective communication. Moreover, the PjBL approach aligns with the principles of authentic assessment, a method in which students demonstrate their learning by performing tasks or solving problems that replicate real-world situations. Authentic assessment prioritizes the application of knowledge and skills in meaningful, practical contexts (Herrington and Herrington (2006); Wiggins (1998)) and evaluates competencies through projects, presentations, portfolios, or other artefacts, rather than standardized testing (Lombardi (2008)).

This paper presents the findings of a student feedback survey conducted at the end of each semester, with particular emphasis on the PjBL assessment component. The study outlines the contextual background and data collection procedures, followed by a detailed analysis of the survey responses. The final section provides a discussion of the results and proposes recommendations for future improvements.

Methodology

Context of the study

The course under examination is a first-year undergraduate course classified as a core STEM subject and recognized as a foundational course that supports the learning of discipline-specific subjects. It is a compulsory course for Business students; however, each year it also attracts a diverse group of students from other programmes, such as Business Information Technology, Informatics and Artificial Intelligence, Food and Biotechnology, Public Administration and Governance, etc., who enrol in it as an elective. As such, the student cohort consists predominantly of non-mathematics majors.

The course employs a combination of traditional assessment methods, such as individual open-book Moodle tests and semi-open-book written and Excel-based in-class tests, alongside a PjBL approach. This PjBL component is referred to as the “final exam” of the course, and it contributes approximately 40% to the overall course grade. The final exam consists of a group project (3 - 4 students per group) that includes the following components: formulating research question(s) based on the group’s area of interest; collecting original data or identifying suitable datasets from public sources; analysing the data using prescribed analytical methods; compiling a research report based on the findings; peer-reviewing another group’s research report; evaluating one’s own and others’ contributions, as well as group dynamics, in the form of a reflection; and participating in an open oral defence of their group’s work through a presentation followed by questions from lecturers and peers. The distinctiveness of this particular task lies primarily in the fact that what is prescribed is the statistical method, not the research question or dataset, as is typically the case. Consequently, students are required to approach the task in reverse: they must begin by considering which types of research

problems and questions could be addressed using the given method. From there, they need to determine what kind of data would be appropriate for such an analysis and how to either collect or source it. This reverse technique requires students to reconceptualize the entire research process from an unconventional perspective - not starting with a theoretical framework and then proceeding to questions and data collection - and in doing so, deepens their understanding of statistical reasoning.

Data and methods of analysis

The data in this study is derived from student feedback collected at the end of each semester through the university's official Study Information System. Although the feedback survey addresses the course as a whole, including its overall content and assessment methods, and does not specifically target the exam project, the responses nevertheless provide partial insights into the PjBL component. Therefore, the general feedback is analysed and interpreted through the lens of the exam project for this study.

The survey in question is structured using Likert-scale statements ranging from "1 – completely disagree" to "5 – completely agree," and comprises three sections: students' self-assessment (3 items), feedback on the course (4 items), and feedback on the lecturer (4 items). In addition to the quantitative items, students may also provide open-ended comments in each section, offering reflections on both positive aspects and perceived shortcomings of the course and the lecturer. For relevance to the present analysis, only the items concerning the course and the lecturer are included in this paper.

The analysis relies on secondary data, as the dataset is pre-existing and was provided to the author in an aggregated form. Accordingly, the quantitative component consists of average values based on aggregated scores across five consecutive academic years. To enrich the analysis and provide additional context, selected excerpts from students' textual commentsⁱ (presented in quotation marks) are incorporated alongside the quantitative findings.

Findings and discussion

This section presents the average values of the survey statements' averages, based on the responses from 410 students collected over five consecutive years (see Figure 1). To further illustrate and contextualize these results, selected direct quotes from students are included to highlight underlying patterns and tendencies.

Figure 1. Five-Year Averages of Student Survey Responses

The responses indicate that the evaluation process is clear and understandable for students (over five years, the maximum average score is 4.93, and the minimum 4.61). This may also suggest that the PjBL component of the assessment is consistently well communicated and effectively implemented throughout the years. This interpretation is supported by one student's words: "The assessment system was simple and understandable for everyone".

Also, the lecturer is seen as an expert in the field and has done a good job teaching the subject (*max* average 4.91, and *min* average 4.41), and giving feedback to the students (*max* average 4.91, and *min* average 4.54). One respondent notes: "The lecturer was a subject matter expert with extensive knowledge in the field, provided relevant examples, and also offered useful recommendations regarding software tools". This is further supported by another student's comment: "[The lecturer] was very good at explaining different concepts clearly and brought in great real-life examples. It's wonderful to see a lecturer who can make a difficult subject easier through their teaching." About giving feedback, one respondent argues: "The feedback was clear, specific, and constructive, with a forward-looking focus on future work and thesis writing".

The learning materials are consistently rated positively, with students highlighting their relevance (*max* average 4.9, and *min* average 4.57). Similarly, the digital learning materials are considered helpful in supporting subject comprehension (*max* average 4.9, and *min* average 4.54). Student comments reinforce these quantitative findings. As one student notes: "The learning materials were relevant, up-to-date, comprehensible, and

aligned with the course content.” Another student reflects specifically on the value of the digital resources: “I also borrowed the textbook, but since the digital materials were very comprehensive, it was not necessary to use the textbook to better understand the course content.”

A slightly lower average score is given to the organisation and structure of the course (*max* average 4.86, and *min* average 4.54). In the open-ended comments, students express criticism regarding two main aspects: the lack of a final report template and the format of group work. Some students suggest that a ready-made, “fill-in-the-blanks” style template for the final report would be helpful. However, this suggestion is not implemented by the lecturers for several reasons. Firstly, throughout the course, lecturers encourage students to explore relevant academic sources, such as journal articles and final theses, particularly focusing on the methodology and methods sections. This approach aims to deepen students’ understanding of discipline-specific literature alongside statistical techniques. Secondly, a predefined template could constrain students within a fixed framework, potentially limiting their creativity in problem-solving and reporting.

The second area of concern relates to the group work format, which is a core component of the assessment, aligned with the PjBL framework. The primary concern relates to the organizational complexity of group work, including challenges in communication, coordination of schedules and pacing, and differing expectations regarding the depth and quality of contributions. Despite these challenges, many students also recognized the value of group work. Over the years, students’ comments have consistently emphasized its benefits. For instance, the respondent notes: “The group project was very engaging and taught us best how to actually do statistics!” Another student points out: “The group project and final assignment were very interesting, and the collaboration with course peers was a pleasant change compared to other subjects. The opportunity to continue the group project as the final assignment was a good and motivating aspect.” A third student summarizes the experience: “I really liked the structure of the exam [*project*] in this course. Although completing it as a group project is somewhat risky, since much depends on the contribution of other group members, we worked very well together, and we all agreed that doing the exam alone using all the statistical formulas would have been too difficult. However, thanks to the way the exam was designed, we were able to practically revisit everything and revise the most important things we had learned.”

The lowest average scores are assigned to the teaching methods employed in the course (*max* average 4.82, and *min* average 4.26). Several factors may explain this pattern. Although part of the assessment integrates PjBL, the overall course structure and the majority of the assessment remain rooted in a traditional lecture-practice format. The course is delivered in a conventional structure where theoretical content is introduced during lectures and reinforced through practice exercises. Moreover, most of the tasks addressed during lectures and practice sessions follow a classical instructional logic: objective → research question → statistical method → analysis → interpretation. In contrast, the final exam, designed as a project, adopts a reversed structure (see discussion above), which may be difficult for students to grasp without prior exposure or practical experience.

Given that this course is classified as a core subject and is intended to provide students with a fundamental theoretical understanding of statistical methods and their underlying mathematical principles, a full transformation into a project-based course is highly complex, if not unfeasible. Therefore, it is unlikely that the teaching format will undergo a major shift shortly, despite student critique. That said, the reversed logic of the exam project, though initially challenging for students, has also received positive feedback. As one student noted: “The exam [*project*] forced us to apply the knowledge we had learned in practice.” Another student added: “The exam [*project*] reflected our understanding and outcomes the most, although the ongoing tests and assessments also contributed significantly.”

Conclusion and educational implications

Five consecutive years of student survey data show consistently high ratings for assessment clarity and fairness, lecturer expertise, feedback quality, and the relevance of learning materials in the course that uses project-based learning as an assessment tool for enhancing statistical literacy. Students’ open-ended comments further suggest that the project’s reversed design logic - beginning with a prescribed statistical method and working backwards to research questions and data - deepens their appreciation of statistical reasoning and its real-world application. Nevertheless, the survey also reveals moderate reservations about the overall teaching methods and the organisational demands of group work. While a full conversion of this core STEM course into a wholly project-based format is impractical, the evidence indicates that targeted adjustments could improve coherence and student experience without sacrificing the rigour required of a foundational statistics module.

Educational recommendations emerge in several areas. Firstly, to scaffold the unfamiliar “method-first” workflow, lecturers could introduce low-stakes micro-projects early in the semester and provide annotated exemplars that illustrate how a chosen analytical technique can guide question formulation and data selection. Secondly, the effectiveness of group work can be improved by offering a brief workshop on team roles and managing conflicts, along with mid-project peer evaluations that help identify unequal participation before the final submission. Additionally, segmenting the final report writing process into distinct stages and submitting sections to lecturers and peers for feedback and presenting preliminary findings already during the course would facilitate a more seamless integration of project-based learning into the course. Implementing these measures could strengthen the alignment between authentic assessment and supportive instruction, foster deeper statistical literacy, and reduce the logistical challenges of collaborative inquiry, all while maintaining the theoretical foundations expected of a core statistics course.

References

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